

PSYCHOLOGICAL METHODS OF EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT ACCORDING TO THE CHILD'S TEMPERAMENT

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Annotation: This article contains the individual psychological feature of the child - the general understanding of the temperature and the methods of educational methods of temperature technique. At the same time, misconceptions according to the child temperament is also covered.

Keywords: individual psychological characteristic, temperament, father - mother, active, "psychological radar", education, "period of crisis", fear.

To date, we can witness the increasing demand and appeals to psychologists in general education schools and social networks regarding child upbringing, parent-child relations, mutual disagreements between them and their elimination. The desire of parents to understand the fate of their children and their inner mental states and their appeals in this regard is certainly a happy situation for us psychologists. But at the same time, the unhealthy psychological environment in the families of some of our mentally disturbed students, their mental depression, disagreements between parents and children make us psychologists think a lot.

So, why are our parents unable to understand the inner states of their children, what they really want and what the real problem is? Why is it that most of our youth are effectively using the opportunities given to them and are moving forward with great goals, while some of their peers are aimless in life, spending most of their time on mobile devices, chatting with people they know and don't know on social networks, and on the streets? The purpose of writing this article is to provide practical psychological help to the family, which is the starting link of our society, that is, parents and their children, and by answering the above questions, to improve their relations, to create a healthy psychological environment in families. Let's start from the beginning. Remember when you held your first child in your arms and how longing and full of joy your heart felt. Over time, your child has reached 2-3 years old. From this very young age, your child begins to recognize and learn about existence through you. He carefully studies your attitude to life, people, all your actions, how you behave in different situations, your inner mental state, that is, whether you are happy or unhappy, calm or nervous, and reflects such states in your mind. It is during this 3-year "period of crisis" that his "inner self" is formed. This means that a small "personality" has been formed that reflects the positive or negative qualities that are dominant in you at that time. Do you know that a child has an internal "psychological radar" through which they sense disagreements between their parents, tense situations and violence in the family.

Psychologists have found that a child is connected to his mother through one "psychological umbilical cord" until the age of 14. If your child grows up in an environment of turmoil, violence or, on the contrary, neglect, it will have a devastating effect on his future. Such children have phobias (fear), low self-esteem and high levels of stress. In this regard, the well-known scientist, doctor, psychologist Tariq Khabib writes about the solution to the problems in raising children:

1. Does your child lie? So you've got it under tight control!
2. Does your child lack self-confidence? So you don't talk to him!
3. Is your child shy? So you are protecting him a lot!
4. Does your child not respect others? So you don't lower your voice around him!
5. Is your child hot? So you don't interact with him!
6. Does your child act aggressively towards others? So you are being rude to him!
7. Is your child weak? So you threaten him a lot!
8. Does your child make you angry? So, you are not paying attention to him!
9. Does your child disturb you and disturb your peace? So you don't hold her in your arms and kiss her cheeks!
10. Does your child disobey you? So you are asking a lot of him!
11. Has your child become a maniac? So you're messing with yourself!

Based on the above, I can say that raising our children to be healthy both physically and mentally, forming positive or negative character traits in them, and what kind of person they will be in the future depends on their parents and the psychological environment in the family. In today's rapidly developing science and technology era, with a high level of social influence, it is not without benefits for our parents to have certain psychological knowledge. Let's get acquainted with the psychological information that is necessary for parents in raising their children, communicating with them, and choosing their children's future professions! We will talk about the essence of the concept of "temperament", which is in the main place in psychology, and its place in child education and development. Most of our parents do not know that the upbringing of a child should be carried out according to his temperament. Temperament is a set of unchangeable innate qualities in a child, which is associated with the characteristics of the child's nervous system. There are 4 types of temperament: Sanguine, Choleric, Melancholic and Phlegmatic. To understand its essence, I will give the following example: one child is happy, another is sad and depressed. One of them laughs and continues playing when he hears his mother's scolding, while the other responds by crying. These 4 types of features are:

1. Sanguine - cheerful, active, enterprising, sleeps quickly and wakes up quickly;
2. Choleric - reactive, active, fluent, quick-witted, impatient;
3. Melancholic - very impressionable, easily bored, difficult to adapt to new conditions, ill-tempered;
4. Phlegmatic - patient, restrained, persistent, speech and actions are slow, and emotions are less changeable.

According to the temperament of the child, the mistakes made in education and the psychological guidelines for their correction:

1. Sanguines. Mistakes in education:

- It is typical for them to postpone parental demands, and they believe in the promise of parents "later";

- Excessive praise;

The correct method is:

- Use of the "now" and "here" method when completing the task for the child;
- Know the limits of praise and express high confidence;

2. Choleric. Mistakes in education:

- Showing anger and aggression to the child;
- Excessive care

The correct method is:

- Speak to the child slowly and gently in order to increase his attention;
- Development of independence in him.

3. Melancholy. Mistakes in education:

- Punishment for unsatisfactory school grades;
- Embarrassing the child in front of strangers.

The correct method is:

- Praise for giving and completing simple tasks;
- To show his positive aspects and achievements in front of others.

4. Phlegmatics. Mistakes in education:

- Delivery of tasks only through words;
- Rewarding their passivity.

The correct method is:

- Demonstrating the performance of the task in practice;
- Increase and reward activity in the team.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that there are 4 types of temperament in one person, only one of them is dominant. Some negative traits can be psychocorrected and changed to a positive side through a positive family environment and education. If you can give your child the support they need to develop, it means you are preparing a healthy member of society. With this, you will help not only the development of our society, but also the prevention of various neurotic diseases and suicidal behavior in our future generations!

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